

Survey Questions - Global Computing Education Research: Current State and Opportunities

The materials presented here are the detailed questions that were used in the paper Global Computing Education Research: Current State and Opportunities, currently submitted to SIGCSE 2023.

The 6 pages limit of SIGCSE didn't allow authors to show the type and depth of the questions made in the survey. This document presents that information.

If the reader just wants to have an idea of the questions asked in the survey, we present a summary of them below. If your goal is to read all questions in detail, the Qualtrics Export of the complete Survey come next. Where it is possible to see that we had different branches created to evaluate different cases: institution that have a CEEd program, institutions that have a joint CEEd program and institutions that don't have a program but have graduate students doing work in the CEEd area.

Summary of survey questions:

Some data that could be relevant to gather in our CSEd Research (National and International):

- Personal Demographics
 - Race/Ethnicity
 - Gender Identity
 - Current Professional Level
- University/College name:
- University/College location:
- University/College focus (research, teaching)
- Is it a minority serving institution?
- Does the University/College have a specific program for CSEd?
 - If yes:
 - Program information
 - Name
 - What school and/or department is the program institutionally?
 - Number or credits or number of courses to graduate
 - List of **mandatory** courses (name, credits, course approach - theoretical, hands on, project?)
 - List of **elective** courses (name, credits, course approach - theoretical, hands on, project?)
 - The program has a minimum amount of publications for students to graduate? If yes, how many? Type of publication (conference, journal)?
 - What percentage of courses are F2F, hybrid, online?
 - Year started

- Student Information
 - Number of students currently registered
 - Graduate (Master's or Ph.D.)
 - Undergraduate
 - Current year of each student
 - Number of graduates (by year, if available)
 - Demographics (on 3 previous questions)
 - Gender
 - Race
 - Ethnicity
 - Nationality
 - Typical time to degree completion, or degree completion information for individual students
- Faculty Information
 - Number of faculty (Instructor, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, Professor)
 - What school or department do they reside in?
 - Demographics (on 3 previous questions)
 - Gender
 - Race
 - Ethnicity
 - Nationality
- If no, but it has PhDs with thesis in the CSEd area of research:
 - General information
 - Number or credits or number of courses to graduate with their thesis
 - List of CSEd courses **offered** (name, credits, course approach - theoretical, hands on, project?)
 - The program has a minimum amount of publications for students to graduate? If yes, how many? Type of publication (conference, journal)?
 - What percentage of courses are F2F, hybrid, online?
 - What field do graduates typically obtain a degree in?
 - Student Information (directly associated with CSEd)
 - Number of students currently registered to complete thesis in CSEd area of research
 - Number of graduates (by year, if available)
 - Current year of each student
 - Demographics (on 3 previous questions)
 - Gender
 - Race
 - Ethnicity
 - Nationality

- Typical time to degree completion, or degree completion information for individual students
- Faculty Information (directly associated with CSEd)
 - Number of faculty
 - What school or department do they reside in?
 - How many faculty members teach CSEd courses?
 - Demographics (on 3 previous questions)
 - Gender
 - Race
 - Ethnicity
 - Nationality
- If no, and does NOT have PhDs with thesis in the CSEd area of research
 - What areas are Ph.D.s typically obtained in?

Complete Qualtrics Survey Flow

Block: Welcome (6 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If

If Does your institution have a formal department/program for Computer Science Education (CSEd) Yes Is Selected

Block: Yes-CSEd (30 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If

If Does your institution have a formal department/program for Computer Science Education (CSEd) No Is Selected

Block: No-CSEd Block (32 Questions)

Branch: New Branch

If

If Does your institution have a formal department/program for Computer Science Education (CSEd) My school does not have a formal department/program designated as CSEd, but it does offer a joint PhD or similar option Is Selected

Block: Joint CSEd Block (32 Questions)

EndSurvey:

Page Break

Start of Block: Welcome

Q1.1 Thank you for agreeing to assist us in our efforts to collect information about graduate programs and faculty that contribute to Computer Science Education (CSEd) research! While we understand you may not be able to provide all the information requested, please do try to complete this data collection tool (or request information from others who may be able to assist) to the best of your abilities. The more detail you can provide, the better, since it will help to create a more complete picture of where CSEd research occurs.

Page Break

Q1.2 What is the name of your institution?

- Other/NotListed (38)
- Aalto University, Finland (76)
- Aarhus University, Denmark (1)
- Bennington College (2)
- Boise State University (3)
- Boston College (4)
- Brigham Young University (5)
- Carnegie Mellon University (6)
- Claremont Graduate University (7)
- Clemson University (8)
- College of St. Scholastica (9)
- Colorado State University (10)
- DePaul University (11)
- Digital Promise (12)
- Drexel University (13)
- Duke University (14)
- Federal University of Santa Catarina (UFSC) (15)
- Florida International University (16)
- Georgia Institute of Technology (17)
- Georgia State University (18)
- Heriot-Watt University (19)

- Indian Institute of Technology Bombay (80)
- Indiana University Bloomington (20)
- KTH Royal Institute of Technology (21)
- Louisiana State University (22)
- Loyola University Chicago (23)
- Marquette University (24)
- Michigan State University (25)
- Michigan Technological University (81)
- Monash University, Australia (74)
- National University of Ireland Galway (26)
- Newcastle University (27)
- New York University (28)
- NORD University (29)
- North Carolina State University (30)
- Northern Kentucky University (31)
- Ohio State University (32)
- Purdue University (83)
- Queen Mary University of London (33)
- Rice University (34)
- Rochester Institute of Technology (82)
- Stanford University (35)

- Tel Aviv University (36)
- Temple University (37)
- University College Dublin (39)
- The University of Adelaide, Australia (73)
- University of Alabama (40)
- University of Auckland, New Zealand (77)
- University of Bologna (41)
- University at Buffalo (42)
- University of California, Berkeley (43)
- University of California, San Diego (44)
- University of Canterbury (45)
- University of Central Lancashire (46)
- University of Chicago (47)
- University of Delaware (48)
- University of Florida (49)
- University of Glasgow (50)
- University of Guelph (51)
- University Of Helsinki, Finland (75)
- University of Illinois at Chicago (52)
- University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign (53)
- University of Lethbridge (54)

- University of Maryland, College Park (55)
 - University of Massachusetts Amherst (56)
 - University of Michigan (57)
 - University of Minnesota (58)
 - University of Nebraska Lincoln (59)
 - University of Nebraska Omaha (60)
 - University of Nevada, Las Vegas (61)
 - University of New Mexico (62)
 - University of Newcastle, Australia (78)
 - University of North Texas (63)
 - University of Pennsylvania (64)
 - University of São Paulo (65)
 - University of Texas at Austin (66)
 - University of Toronto, Canada (72)
 - University of Washington (67)
 - Uppsala University, Sweden (79)
 - Victoria University of Wellington (68)
 - Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University (69)
 - Washington State University (70)
 - Western University (71)
-

Display This Question:

If What is the name of your institution? = Other/NotListed

Q1.3 Please enter the name of your institution.

Q1.4 What is the location of your institution?

City (1) _____

State or Province (If Applicable) (2)

Country (3) _____

Q1.5 What is your current professional level or title:

Undergraduate Student (1)

Master's Student (2)

PhD Student (3)

Post-Doctorate (4)

Professor/Faculty (5)

Other (6) _____

Page Break _____

Q1.8 Does your institution have a formal department/program for Computer Science Education (CSEd)

Yes (1)

No (2)

My school does not have a formal department/program designated as CSEd, but it does offer a joint PhD or similar option (4)

Page Break

End of Block: Welcome

Start of Block: Yes-CSEd

Q2Intro Please answer the following questions about your Computer Science Education (CSEd) department/program:

Q2.1 What is the name of your CSEd department/program?

Q2.2 What is the name of the school/college that your CSEd department/program belongs to?

Q2.3 How many credits are required to graduate with a PhD at your institution in CSEd (if applicable)?

Q2.4 How many courses are required to graduate with a PhD at your institution in CSEd (if applicable)?

Q2.5 Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in CSEd?

- Yes, there is a formal requirement (2)
- Yes, there is an informal requirement (3)
- No (4)

Display This Question:

If Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in CSEd? = Yes, there is a formal requirement

Or Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in CSEd? = Yes, there is an informal requirement

Q2.5b Please enter the number required and specify whether this is a conference publication, journal publication, or either.

Q2.6 For each course that is mandatory for a graduate degree in CSEd, please list the name, number of credits, and course description.

Q2.7 For each course that is mandatory for a graduate degree in CSEd, please attach the syllabus as a PDF, or as a zipped folder of PDFs.

Q2.8 For any course that is offered as an elective for a graduate degree in CSEd, please list the name, number of credits, and course description.

Q2.9 If available, please attach the syllabus of all elective courses as a PDF, or as a zipped folder of PDFs.

Q2.10 What year was the department/program established?

Q2.11 If one exists, please provide the link to the website for your department/program:

Page Break

Q2AllStudents All Students: Please answer the following questions about the students in your Computer Science Education (CSEd) department/program:

Q2.12 How many students are currently registered in CSEd?

0 20 40 60 80 100 120 140 160 180 200

Q2.13 What is the typical time to degree completion in your department/program:

Page Break

Q2AllPhDs PhD Students: If you are able, please try to obtain the following information from your graduate chair or office. Otherwise, please try to answer according to your best knowledge about your peers in the Computer Science Education (CSEd) department/program:

Q2.14 Please list the break down of the current year for each of your PhD students (e.g., 1st year-15; 2nd year-22)

Q2.15 How many PhD graduates has the CSEd program had? Please list by year if information is available.

Q2.16 In the current academic year, please estimate what percentage of students in the CSEd program are domestic and what percentage are international students?

Domestic (1) _____

International (2) _____

Q2.17 How are graduate studies financially supported? [Check all that apply]:

- Training grant (1)
- Research grant (primarily working on my own research) (2)
- Research grant (primarily working on someone else' research) (3)
- Scholarship or Fellowship (4)
- Teaching Assistantship (5)
- Graduate Assistantship (Neither teaching nor research) (6)
- University or department fellowships (7)
- Loans (8)
- Personal resources (9)

Page Break _____

Q2Faculty Faculty: Please answer the following questions about the faculty affiliated with your Computer Science Education (CSEd) department/program:

Q2.18 How many faculty are part of the Computer Science Education department/program?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Q2.19 Please list all any schools/colleges or departments these faculty reside in/have affiliations with:

Q2.20 What are the gender pronouns used by faculty in your department/program that are active for the current school year?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

She/Her/Hers ()	
He/His/Him ()	
They/Them/Theirs ()	
Ze/Zir/Zirs ()	
Ze/Hir/Hirs ()	
Faculty member prefers not to answer/Does not specify ()	

Q2.21 What are the known nationalities of the faculty in your department/program for the current school year?

Q2.22 Please list the first and last names of any faculty members at your institution that conduct Computer Science Education (CSEd) research:

Q2.23 For any faculty members and/or groups/labs at your institution that conduct Computer Science Education (CSEd) research, please list any active awards from within the last two years:

	PI Name (First and Last) (4)	Award Source (e.g., NSF, NIH) (5)	Award Number (6)	Award Amount (7)	Award Duration (8)
1 (7)					
2 (8)					
3 (9)					
4 (10)					
5 (11)					
6 (12)					
7 (13)					
8 (14)					
9 (15)					

10 (16)					
11 (17)					
12 (18)					
13 (19)					
14 (20)					
15 (21)					
16 (22)					
17 (23)					
18 (24)					
19 (25)					

20 (26)

Q2.24 Are there any plans to add more faculty in CSEd at your institution in the next 5 years?
Please elaborate.

Page Break

Q2Closing You have reached the end of the data collection tool. If you would like to go back and revise any of your responses, please do so now. Otherwise click the arrow on the right to submit.

End of Block: Yes-CSEd

Start of Block: No-CSEd Block

Q3Intro Please answer the following questions about obtaining a graduate degree in a field related to Computer Science Education (CSEd) at your institution, and courses that may be offered towards the degree:

Q3.1 Does your institution offer a PhD title related to Computer Science Education (e.g., STEM Education, Education Tech, Engineering Education)?

Yes (1)

No (2)

Display This Question:

If Does your institution offer a PhD title related to Computer Science Education (e.g., STEM Educati... = Yes

Q3.2 If one exists, please provide the link to the website for your department/program:

Q3.3 What term(s) best describes the name of the graduate degree(s) awarded in Computer Science Education? Please select all that apply.

- Master of Arts (MA) (8)
- Master of Science (MS, MSc) (9)
- Master of Education (ME) (10)
- Master of Education (MEd, MEd, MIT, MAEd, MAT) (15)
- Master of Research (MRes) (11)
- Master by Research (MPhil) (12)
- Master of Studies (MSt) (13)
- Master of Engineering (MEng) (16)
- Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (1)
- Doctor of Education (EdD) (4)
- Certificate Program (14)
- Other (7)

Display This Question:

If What term(s) best describes the name of the graduate degree(s) awarded in Computer Science Educat... = Other

Q3.3a Please specify the term(s) for the "Other" graduate degree(s):

Q3.4 What term(s) best describes the field in which a graduate degree(s) is awarded in Computer Science Education? Please select all that apply.

- Bioinformatics (6)
- Computer Science (1)
- Computational Science and Engineering (7)
- Computer Science and Applications (10)
- Computer Science and Learning Sciences (3)
- Education (2)
- Education, Career and Technical Education (11)
- Engineering Education (4)
- Human-Centered Computing (8)
- Machine Learning (9)
- Psychology (12)
- Physics (13)
- Philosophy (14)
- Statistics (15)
- STEM Education (5)
- Other (16)

Display This Question:

If What term(s) best describes the field in which a graduate degree(s) is awarded in Computer Scienc... = Other

Q3.4a Please specify the term(s) for the "Other" field:

Q3.5 At your institution, which school/department(s) do students belong to that are working towards a PhD in a field related to Computer Science Education?

Q3.6 How many PhD graduates does your institution have associated with a PhD title related to Computer Science Education? Please list by year if information is available. (Ex. 2020 - 12; 2019 - 19, etc...)

Q3.7 What is the typical time to degree completion for students working towards a PhD in CSEd in your department/program (from the time they start until they graduate and finish the program):

Page Break

Q3.8 How many credits are required to graduate with a PhD in your program/department?

Q3.9 How many courses are required to graduate with a PhD in your program/department?

Q3.10 Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in your program/department?

- Yes, there is a formal requirement (1)
- Yes, there is an informal requirement (2)
- No (3)

Display This Question:

If Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in your p... = Yes, there is a formal requirement

Or Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in your p... = Yes, there is an informal requirement

Q3.10b Please enter the number required and specify whether this is a conference publication, journal publication, or either.

Q3.11 If any exist, please describe any computer science education specific courses offered at your institution (Listing the name, number of credits, and course description).

Q3.12 If available, please attach the syllabus for each computer science education specific course offered at your institution as a PDF, or as a zipped folder of PDFs.

Q3.13 Do the computer science education specific courses offered count towards the PhD degree?

- Yes, they can be used towards the degree directly as elective credits (1)
- No, they cannot be used towards the degree, and are additional courses (2)
- Other (3)

Q3.14 Are there any plans to create a CSEd program at your institution in the next five years?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Are there any plans to create a CSEd program at your institution in the next five years? = Yes

Q3.14a Please describe what your institution is considering:

Page Break

Q3PhD PhD Students: If you are able, please try to obtain the following information from your graduate chair or office. Otherwise, please try to answer it according to your best knowledge about your peers at the PhD in your department/program:

Q3.15 Please list the break down of the current year for each of your PhD students (e.g., 1st year-15; 2nd year-22).

Q3.16 In the current academic year, please estimate what percentage of students in your program are domestic and what percentage are international students?

Domestic (4) _____

International (5) _____

Q3.17 How are graduate studies financially supported? [Check all that apply]:

- Training grant (1)
- Research grant (primarily working on my own research) (2)
- Research grant (primarily working on someone else' research) (3)
- Scholarship or Fellowship (4)
- Teaching Assistantship (5)
- Graduate Assistantship (Neither teaching nor research) (6)
- University or department fellowships (7)
- Loans (8)
- Personal resources (9)

Page Break

Q3Faculty Faculty: Please answer the following questions about the faculty conducting Computer Science Education (CSEd) research at your institution:

Q3.18 How many faculty conduct Computer Science Education research at your institution?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Q3.19 Please list all any schools/colleges or departments these faculty reside in/have affiliations with:

Q3.20 What are the gender pronouns used by faculty in your department/program that are active for the current school year?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

She/Her/Hers ()	
He/His/Him ()	
They/Them/Theirs ()	
Ze/Zir/Zirs ()	
Ze/Hir/Hirs ()	
Faculty member prefers not to answer/Does not specify ()	

Q3.21 What are the known nationalities of the faculty in your department/program for the current school year?

Q3.22 Please list the first and last names of any faculty members and/or groups/labs at your institution that conduct Computer Science Education (CSEd) research:

Q3.23 For any faculty members and/or groups/labs at your institution that conduct Computer Science Education (CSEd) research, please list any active awards from within the last two years:

	PI Name (First and Last) (4)	Award Source (e.g., NSF, NIH) (5)	Award Number (6)	Award Amount (7)	Award Duration (8)
1 (7)					
2 (8)					
3 (9)					
4 (10)					
5 (11)					
6 (12)					
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17 (23)					
18 (24)					
19 (25)					

20 (26)

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Q3.24 Are there any plans to add more faculty in CSEd at your institution in the next 5 years?
Please elaborate.

Page Break

Q3Closing You have reached the end of the data collection tool. If you would like to go back and revise any of your responses, please do so now. Otherwise click the arrow on the right to submit.

End of Block: No-CSEd Block

Start of Block: Joint CSEd Block

Q4Intro Please answer the following questions about your joint degree program:

Q4.1 What term(s) best describes the degree(s) that graduate students can obtain in your joint degree program? Please select all that apply.

- Master of Arts (MA) (8)
- Master of Science (MS, MSc) (9)
- Master of Education (ME) (10)
- Master of Education (MEd, MEd, MIT, MAEd, MAT) (15)
- Master of Research (MRes) (11)
- Master by Research (MPhil) (12)
- Master of Studies (MSt) (13)
- Master of Engineering (MEng) (16)
- Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (1)
- Doctor of Education (EdD) (4)
- Certificate Program (14)
- Other (7)

Display This Question:

*If What term(s) best describes the degree(s) that graduate students can obtain in your joint degree...
= Other*

Q4.1a Please specify the term(s) for the "Other" graduate degree(s):

Q4.2 What term(s) best describes the field(s) that graduate students are part of in your joint degree program? Please select all that apply.

- Bioinformatics (6)
- Computer Science (1)
- Computational Science and Engineering (7)
- Computer Science and Applications (10)
- Computer Science and Learning Sciences (3)
- Education (2)
- Education, Career and Technical Education (11)
- Engineering Education (4)
- Human-Centered Computing (8)
- Machine Learning (9)
- Psychology (12)
- Physics (13)
- Philosophy (14)
- Statistics (15)
- STEM Education (5)
- Other (16)

Display This Question:

If What term(s) best describes the field(s) that graduate students are part of in your joint degree... = Other

Q4.2a Please specify the term(s) for the "Other" field:

Q4.3 At your institution, which school/department(s) do students belong to that are working towards a PhD in a field related to Computer Science Education?

Q4.4 How many PhD graduates does your institution have associated with its joint degree program? Please list by year if information is available.

Q4.5 What is the typical time to degree completion for PhD students in your joint degree program:

Q4.6 If one exists, please provide the link to the website for your joint degree program:

Page Break

Q4.7 How many credits are required to graduate with a PhD in your joint degree program (if applicable)?

Q4.8 How many courses are required to graduate with a PhD in your joint degree program (if applicable)?

Q4.9 Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in your joint degree program?

- Yes, there is a formal requirement (1)
- Yes, there is an informal requirement (2)
- No (3)

Display This Question:

If Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in your j... = Yes, there is a formal requirement

Or Are there a minimum number of publications required for students to graduate with a PhD in your j... = Yes, there is an informal requirement

Q4.9a Please enter the number required and specify whether this is a conference publication, journal publication, or either.

Q4.10 If any exist, please describe any computer science education specific courses offered at your institution (Listing the name, number of credits, and course description).

Q4.11 If available, please attach the syllabus for each computer science education specific course offered at your institution as a PDF, or as a zipped folder of PDFs.

Q4.12 Do the computer science education specific courses offered count towards the PhD in your joint degree program?

- Yes, they can be used towards the degree directly as elective credits (4)
- No, they cannot be used towards the degree and are additional courses (5)
- Other (6) _____

Q4.13 Are there any plans to create a CSEd program at your institution in the next five years?

- Yes (1)
- No (2)

Display This Question:

If Are there any plans to create a CSEd program at your institution in the next five years? = Yes

Q4.13a Please describe what your institution is considering:

Page Break

Q4PhD PhD Students: If you are able, please try to obtain the following information from your graduate chair or office. Otherwise, please try to answer it according to your best knowledge about your peers at the PhD in your joint degree department/program:

Q4.14 Please list the break down of the current year for each of your PhD students (e.g., 1st year-15; 2nd year-22).

Q4.15 In the current academic year, please estimate what percentage of students in the joint degree program are domestic and what percentage are international students?

Domestic (2) _____

International (3) _____

Q4.16 How are your graduate studies financially supported? [Check all that apply]

- Training grant (1)
- Research grant (primarily working on my own research) (2)
- Research grant (primarily working on someone else' research) (3)
- Scholarship or Fellowship (4)
- Teaching Assistantship (5)
- Graduate Assistantship (Neither teaching nor research) (6)
- University or department fellowships (7)
- Loans (8)
- Personal resources (9)

Page Break _____

Q4Faculty Faculty: Please answer the following questions about the faculty in the joint degree program:

Q4.17 How many faculty are part of your joint degree program?

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Q4.18 How many faculty in your joint degree program **conduct** Computer Science Education **research** at your institution

0 10 20 30 40 50 60 70 80 90 100

Q4.19 Please list all any schools/colleges or departments other than the joint degree program that these faculty reside in/have affiliations with:

Q4.20 What are the gender pronouns used by faculty in your joint degree program that are active for the current school year?

Q4.21 What are the known nationalities of the faculty in your joint degree program for the current school year?

Q4.22 Please list the first and last names of any faculty members and/or groups/labs at your institution that conduct Computer Science Education (CSEd) research:

Q4.23 For any faculty members and/or groups/labs at your institution that conduct Computer Science Education (CSEd) research, please list any active awards from within the last two years

	PI Name (First and Last) (4)	Award Source (e.g., NSF, NIH) (5)	Award Number (6)	Award Amount (7)	Award Duration (8)
1 (7)					
2 (8)					
3 (9)					
4 (10)					
5 (11)					
6 (12)					
7 (13)					
8 (14)					
9 (15)					

10 (16)					
11 (17)					
12 (18)					
13 (19)					
14 (20)					
15 (21)					
16 (22)					
17 (23)					
18 (24)					
19 (25)					

20 (26)

Q4.24 Are there any plans to add more faculty in CSEd at your institution in the next 5 years?
Please elaborate.

Page Break

Q4Closing You have reached the end of the data collection tool. If you would like to go back and revise any of your responses, please do so now. Otherwise click the arrow on the right to submit.

End of Block: Joint CSEd Block
